

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF GENDER IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: English and Uzbek both incorporate gendered pronouns and occupation titles, yet they diverge significantly in their treatment of grammatical gender, gender agreement, and language structure. Unlike English, which lacks grammatical gender for nouns, Uzbek assigns nouns into masculine, feminine, and neuter categories, impacting agreement patterns. Uzbek often indicates gender through suffixes or affixes, contrasting with English's reliance on word order and context. Cultural influences also shape gender expression in language differently in each case. These distinctions emphasize the necessity of considering both linguistic and cultural aspects when analyzing gender expression in language.

Key words: Gender, language, similarities, differences, pronouns, grammatical gender, gender agreement, occupation titles, possessive pronouns, cultural influence.

Annotatsiya: Ingliz va o'zbek tillari jinsga munosabatda, masalan, jins olmoshlari va kasb unvonlarini qo'llashda o'xshashliklarga ega bo'lsa-da, ular grammatik jins, gender kelishuvi va til tuzilishi jihatidan sezilarli farqlarni ko'rsatadi. Ingliz tilida otlar uchun grammatik jins yo'q, o'zbek tilida esa otlarni erkak, ayol va betaraf jinslarga ajratadi, bu esa kelishik shakllariga ta'sir qiladi. Bundan tashqari, o'zbek tilida jinsni ko'rsatish uchun ko'pincha qo'shimchalar yoki affikslar qo'llaniladi, bu ingliz tilining so'z tartibi va kontekstga bog'liqligiga qarama-qarshidir.

Madaniy ta'sirlar ham har bir tilda jinsga lingvistik munosabatni har xil shakllantiradi. Ushbu farqlar tilda jinsning qanday ifodalanishini o'rganishda ham lingvistik, ham madaniy omillarni hisobga olishni ta'kidlaydi.
Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz, o'zbek, jins, til, o'xshashliklar, farqlar, olmoshlar, grammatik jins, jins kelishuvi, kasb unvonlari, egalik olmoshlari, madaniy ta'sir.

Although both English and Uzbek languages utilize grammar as a fundamental means of expressing gender, their methodologies diverge. In English, gender is often implied through pronouns such as "he" and "she,"

without inherent gender markers on nouns. For instance, "doctor" is gender-neutral in English. In contrast, Uzbek utilizes grammatical gender, assigning nouns to masculine, feminine, or neuter categories. For example, "doctor" in Uzbek, "tabib," is masculine ("tabib" for a male doctor and "tabib" for a female doctor). Despite these differences, both languages rely on grammar to convey gender, underscoring the importance of linguistic analysis and cultural context in language comprehension.

There is a regular correspondence between English nouns and the personal pronouns in the third person singular he, she, it. But this correspondence is not equal with the one which is found in Russian. In the Russian language this correspondence is based on both the lexical-semantic and the grammatical aspects but in English it is based on only the lexical-semantic aspect, that is "he" is usually used to indicate real biological male sex, "she" indicates real biological female sex and "It" is used to indicate inanimate objects. It is important to remember that the pronouns he, she, may also be used with regard to inanimate nouns. Such a use of these pronouns is explained by the cultural and historical backgrounds and it has nothing to do with the grammatical expression of the meaning of gender. Examples: moon - she, ship - she, love - he and so on. Summing up the problem of gender in Modern English, it is important to say that: 1. gender is the grammatical distinction between; masculine, feminine and neuter; 2. the lexical - grammatical category of gender existed only in the OE period but in ME (middle English) this category has been lost [Iriskulov;22]. **"She** is a strict but fair teacher."

"Qiziq **u** kotelokni mahkam changallab olgan, qo'yib yuborgisi kelmasdi." [Ikki eshik orasi; 208] English Sentence: **"She** is a strict but fair teacher." [Harry; 89] This English sentence uses the feminine pronoun **"she"** to refer to the teacher. It implies that the teacher is female. The gendered pronoun "she" indicates the gender of the teacher as feminine. Uzbek Sentence: "Qiziq, **u** kotelokni mahkam changaallab olgan, qo'yib yuborgisi kelmasdi." [Ikki eshik orasi; 208] The Uzbek sentence does not explicitly state the gender of the subject. The pronoun **"u"** is gender-neutral and can refer to a person of any gender. Therefore, without additional context, we cannot determine the gender of the subject in the Uzbek sentence.

Overall, while both English and Uzbek languages share some similarities in how they handle gender, such as the use of gendered pronouns, they exhibit significant differences in grammatical gender, gender agreement, language structure, and cultural influence. Understanding these similarities and

differences is essential for effective communication and language proficiency in both languages.

Gender “tushunchasi feministik nazariya va gendershunoslikning rivojlanishi tufayli keng tarqaldi. U ijtimoiy konstruktivizm nazariyasiga asoslanadi, ularning bir qator vakillari (asosan feministik mualliflar) odamlar o‘rtasidagi farqlarning tabiiy kelib chiqishini shubha ostiga qo‘yadilar va ularni ijtimoiy jarayonlar bilan izohlaydilar. Shunday qilib, „gender“ tushunchasi „biologiya taqdir sifatida“ haqidagi oddiy g‘oyalarni tanqid qilish uchun mo‘ljallangan va gender tengligi mafkurasiga ishora qiladi.

The term “gender” is opposed to the term “sex” (пол). The first term (gender) is a pure grammatical term which deals with the grammatical expression of grammatical gender, i.e., the expression of masculine, feminine and neuter genders. The second word (sex) is used as a common word for both male and female. Thus, it is often used to denote biological notions. Speaking about the Modern English language we can say that the English nouns do not have a grammatical category of gender. It is because that the nouns do not have constant grammatical means to express the gender 21 distinctions [Iriskulov;21]

Similarities:

- Both English and Uzbek use gendered pronouns.
- Gender influences language use and understanding in both languages.
- Grammar plays a significant role in shaping gender expression in both languages.

Differences:

- English lacks grammatical gender for nouns, while Uzbek categorizes nouns into masculine, feminine, and neuter genders.
- Uzbek employs gender agreement and suffixes to indicate gender, while English relies more on word order and context.
- Cultural influences shape gender expression differently in each language.

In conclusion, although there are resemblances in gender expression between the two languages, disparities arise in their grammatical structures and cultural underpinnings

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